

Influence of Art Pedagogics on Adolescents with Deviant Behavior and Children with Disabilities

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Abstract

The need for social interaction between children with disabilities and their peers, which indicates the degree of educational inclusion in schools, fostered this research. There is an insufficiently developed methodological framework for organizing interpersonal relations in the field of inclusive education. This research aims to develop the methodology based on art pedagogics used to involve adolescents with deviant behavior to work with children with disabilities. The leading method in the study of the research problem is the method of natural pedagogical experiment. The experiment was conducted on the basis of Mirny School No.7 among students from grades 2-4 and 7-9. The results of the experiment helped to create the methodological guide for adolescences to work with children with disabilities, establish "ArtStudio" on the basis of Mirny School No.7. Also, there were positive changes in personality and character of adolescents with behavioral problems and improvement of social adaptation of children with disabilities. The authors developed the technology that facilitates the introduction of art pedagogics into the educational environment which is unique for psychological and pedagogical support of children. The experience of attracting teenagers with deviant behavior to work with children with disabilities in Mirny School No.7 might help other schools to create similar environment to promote inclusive education.

Keywords: art pedagogics, adolescents, deviant behavior, art studio, children with disabilities.

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Introduction

Modern education is at a critical stage of its development. Being a mirror of the society, it constantly searches for new methods and technologies that can help the teacher to achieve the educational goal that is to train and educate a harmonically developing citizen who is able to create (Kulchitskaya, 2014). With the introduction of the Federal state educational system, the requirements for teachers to use a variety of educational technologies and forms of work to ensure conditions for the personal development of a child are increasing.

The problem of socio-psychological adaptation and socialization of children with developmental disabilities in the society is thoroughly studied by researchers (Rozenal, Akhmetzyanova, & Artemyeva, 2018). It is necessary to mention that in recent years, scientific attention to the problems of children's disability has significantly increased due to the following circumstances. First, there has been the increase in the number of children with disabilities which is why a new social group is being formed. Second, social problems maximize the potential of children with disabilities on the background of reducing the total fertility rate (Vasilievna, 2018).

In the search for effective means of correction, modern special psychology and pedagogy are increasingly focused on the use of arts in the process of teaching and raising children with developmental disorders (Levchenko, Medvedeva, Komissarova, & Dobrovolskaya, 2001).

The introduction of inclusive education in educational institutions, aimed at humanizing education, does not always have positive results. One of the problems is the manifestation of aggression of adolescents with deviant behavior in relation to students with disabilities. To solve this problem, it is necessary to use new social and pedagogical technologies. One of these technologies is social and pedagogical support (Dorokhova, Galaguzova, & Volgina, 2018).

In this regard, the research problem of this study stemmed from an insufficiently developed methodological framework for organizing interpersonal relations in the field of inclusive education.

Art pedagogics, as a pedagogical technology based on the synthesis of artistic, creative and game activities of students, provides the maximum opportunities for the development of subjective activity of the student (Taranova, 2006).

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is to develop a methodology for attracting adolescents with deviant behavior to work with children with disabilities using the techniques of art pedagogics.

Literature review

The well-known "Republic of SHKID", written by Belykh and Panteleev (1927), former mentees of the Dostoevsky School for students with learning disabilities and disruptive behavior, is a striking example of the use of art pedagogics in the work with adolescents with deviant and disruptive behavior. "It was necessary to determine firmly the style of education, the motives. (...) The main method of our school is the following: constant supervision, pedagogical use of all the mental characteristics of pupils and a proper direction of their mental energy because in many cases they became difficult to educate as their mental energy did not find an appropriate outlet and was spent either in vain or in ugly forms" (Soroka-Rosinsky, 1978). Physical training, drawing, singing, and dancing was added to General education subjects. Soroka-Rosinsky (1978) wanted to create the school where children learned about the world in the process of creativity and had the opportunity to open up and express themselves.

One of the major causes of deviant behavior is a systematic school failure. Increasing failures lead to a complete lack of desire to learn which is why it is appropriate to help teenagers with deviant behavior to realize their own potential by organizing their leisure activities and creating conditions for the formation of the sense of demand. By creating favorable external (art pedagogical) conditions for the disclosure of the inner potential of the individual, it is possible to actualize and stimulate the constructive self-realization of the individual and the definition of acceptable (necessary and sufficient) living conditions (Anisimov, 2003).

Methodology

Research methods applied in this study are survey, conversations, observation, studying the products of students' activities (notebooks, creative works), studying of school documentation (personal files of students, medical records, class logs, student diaries), the registration method, natural pedagogical experiment.

600 children study at Mirny School No.7, including 30 children with different types of disabilities. In grades 7-9, there is a manifestation of aggression of teenagers with deviant behavior towards children with disabilities. Thus, during the research the following steps were implemented: an initial survey, conducting a seminar for teenagers, the follow-up survey, training sessions for teenagers on the didactics used with younger students with disabilities.

Results

Initial survey

The survey was conducted among students aged 12-15 years, the number of respondents – 94 people, including 5 teenagers with deviant behavior. Students were offered a questionnaire "Inclusive education through the eyes of teenagers" which was developed by the teacher-psychologist of the Mirny School No.7.

The first question of the questionnaire was: "Please tell me, do you know what inclusive education is?". Based on the answers to this question, we can conclude that half of the respondents (46%) do not know what inclusive education is. From the subsequent conversation, it turned out that the teenagers did not understand the term "inclusive education".

"Where do you think children with disabilities should study?" – 33% of the respondents said that they should be trained on an equal basis with everyone else, in a mainstream class. 29% believed that such children should be educated in a special school. Only 3% of teenagers said they did not care where students with disabilities are educated. Given the specifics of puberty, we deliberately included such answer options as "I do not care" and "I cannot answer" in the questionnaire.

The next question in the questionnaire was: "Are you ready to take part in projects on working with children with disabilities and children with learning difficulties?". 50% of the respondents said that they are ready, 24% of the students did not want to take part in such projects, 26% did not answer at the time of the survey.

The next question was rather provocative: "How do you feel about having a disabled child or a child with disabilities in your class?" 59% of respondents answered positively, 33% of students were indifferent, only 3% of the students responded negatively, and 5% found it difficult to answer.

When asked about providing any assistance to people with disabilities, 67% of students answered affirmatively, 29% said that perhaps they would assist, 2% of the respondents were not ready to help, and another 2% of the students experienced difficulties in answering.

Answering the question: "What positive or negative aspects do you see when teaching healthy children and children with disabilities together?", 38% of respondents believed that co-education allows children with disabilities to get good education; 18% believed that co-education can prepare society to accept people with disabilities; 18% of the respondents noted that all participants in the educational process form kindness, empathy, and a desire to help.

When asked to enumerate negative aspects of inclusive education, 29% of the school children named such factor that children with disabilities can become a target for ridicule; 5% of respondents believed that they did not have friends among their peers so they might feel like outcast; 4% believed that bullying by healthy peers can lead to the formation of negative character traits in children with special educational needs. Since this question was open-ended, the rest of the survey participants gave different answers or left the column empty.

Thus, the results of the survey revealed the attitude of adolescents to inclusive education: a fairly large percentage of adolescents (29%) believe that children with disabilities should be educated in a special school. Also, the negative aspects of inclusive education, according to 29% of respondents, are negative attitudes of peers and bullying. However, 67% of the respondents expressed a positive or neutral attitude to children with disabilities who study with them in the same school, which allowed us to continue the pedagogical experiment.

Conducting a seminar for teenagers

At this stage, the work continued with teenagers who expressed positive or neutral attitudes to children with disabilities. Also, there were five teenagers with deviant behavior. The goal was to motivate teenagers to work with children with disabilities. The following methods of emotional support were used:

- mismatch of information contained in statements with the established views and opinions of listeners;
- the speaker's use of works of art, vivid illustrations, colorful examples, sharp digital juxtaposition or contrast;
- gradation, rhetorical questions, question-and-answer form of speech, voice design, use of appropriate facial expressions and gestures, emotional exclamations;

It is known that many teenagers, especially teenagers with deviant behavior, have experienced emotional rejection, so it is at the emotional level that they can find a large number of emotionally rejected people. From the very beginning, they were presented with illustrations of such people as Van Gogh, Beethoven and other famous people who had some learning disabilities and developmental disorders, used their examples to reflect on the concept of "successful person; such qualities as "intelligence, beauty, recognition in society, prosperity" were also quoted. Later, the participants came to the conclusion that such concepts do not always describe people who contribute to the society and that a person with special needs can be an

ordinary member of the society, who has the right to human goods like every other individual. At the end of the seminar, the participating children were invited to take part in the establishment of an art studio and take patronage over primary school children, including children with disabilities.

At this stage, it was of great importance that the involvement of teenagers with deviant behavior in work helps them, first of all, to realize their potential, which they cannot show in educational activities since most of them are lagging behind. In the project, they not only assist in the socialization of children with disabilities but also show their skills and knowledge while realizing their own self-importance and relevance.

Follow-up survey

The follow-up survey of 95 people, conducted after the workshop, showed that 89% of respondents are ready to help children with disabilities. The result increased by 22% compared to the results of the initial survey. 21% of the respondents (the indicator decreased by 8%) answered that they are ready to work with children identified with developmental disorders and learning difficulties. 1% of the students were not ready to help younger children. The rest of the participants found it difficult to answer.

7% of the respondents (23% higher than in the previous survey) expressed their willingness to participate in projects related to children with disabilities and children with developmental disorders. 16% of the students (the indicator decreased by 8%) do not want to participate in such projects. 11% found it difficult to answer the question.

64% of the students (the index increased by 31%) said that children with disabilities should be taught on an equal basis with everyone else in a mainstream class. 15% of the respondents believed that they should study in a special school. 2% of the respondents were indifferent to the issue.

Thus, methods of emotional influence on teenagers gave a positive result. However, there were fears that having faded emotionally, the teenagers would not be ready to continue working. Out of the 40 people who were ready to take part in the project, only 15 came to the first training seminar. We believe that we made a mistake by taking a break (1 week) between the workshop and the beginning of the training sessions. During that week we needed to learn more about the personalities of these teenagers which is why we conducted interviews with teachers and social educators, studied the products of students' activities (notebooks, creative works) and school documentation (personal files of students, medical records, class logs, student diaries), analyzed academic performance, and made individual maps of the capabilities of the teenager.

Training sessions for teenagers on the didactics used with younger students with disabilities

The purpose of the first training session on the topic "Basics of art pedagogics" was to immerse teenagers in the world of art pedagogics and develop a program for further joint activities. In the future, it was planned to hold four more training sessions on the topics of "Drawing", "Modeling", "Physical activity" and "Rhythm", to present a lesson plan and basic methods of work.

This stage is currently incomplete due to the emerging epidemiological situation in the world and in the Russian Federation due to the spread of COVID-19. Since schools and higher education institutions switched to distance learning, our project temporarily slowed down. At the moment, we organized remote consulting and support programs for adolescents. The social network Instagram produces videos on the basics of art pedagogics, methods of working with children, as well as recommendations. There are also online meetings in the Zoom where we answer students' questions. The final survey and summing up will be completed after the project is resumed.

Thus, we achieved the following results:

- project participants (2 teenagers) became winners of the 3rd Republican festival-competition of inclusive creativity (Yakutsk);
- the methodological guide on art pedagogics for adolescents working with children with disabilities was developed;
- the online course "Involving teenagers with deviant behavior in working with children with disabilities" was started.

Also, during the research project we created the "Art Studio" in the Mirny School No.7 that works on a permanent basis. Another important interim result achieved during the project were positive changes in the personality and character of adolescents with deviant behavior and improvement of social adaptation of children with disabilities.

Discussions

In this paper, the art pedagogic is considered as a method of correction of deviant behavior of teenagers in school and social adaptation of children with disabilities. Since social interactions between children with disabilities and their peers are not only important for the development of their social competence but can also indicate the degree of educational inclusion in secondary schools (Rodrigues, Menezes, & Beckmann, 2019).

One of the major causes of deviant behavior is the systematic school failure. Increasing failure leads to a complete lack of desire to learn. As a result, the teenager has a lot of free time, since there are no cognitive aspirations, or tasks that interest him or her (Kalinina, Artamonova, & Salakhova, 2017). That is why it is appropriate to help a teenager with deviant behavior to realize their own potential by organizing their leisure activities and creating conditions for the formation of a sense of demand. That is why an Art Studio, where difficult teenagers are engaged with younger students with disabilities is a way to assist students with deviant behavior with an aim of their social adaptation.

Conclusion

According to the results of the survey in the Mirny School No.7, attitudes of teenagers to children with disabilities are either positive or neutral, which allowed us to continue the pedagogical experiment. Using methods of emotional influence, as shown by repeated surveys, we were able to increase the level of motivation of teenagers in art pedagogics classes with children with disabilities. The introduction of art pedagogic into the educational space would be unique for psychological and pedagogical support of children. The experience of involving teenagers with deviant behavior in working with children with learning disabilities and developmental disorders in Mirny School No.7 might potentially help other schools create conditions for the successful implementation of the inclusive education environment.

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